

spittlebugs with different host plant and habitat associations, with implications for behavioural characteristics, e.g. mobility. In this study, we evaluated trap catches of sharpshooter vectors at 2.5 m and 7.5 m above ground as a measure of mobility, in areas surrounding citrus groves in two localities (Botucatu and Casa Branca) of São Paulo State, Brazil. Three yellow sticky cards of 10 x 30 cm were used per trapping height on several bamboo stakes positioned in areas surrounding citrus groves in the municipalities of Botucatu and Casa Branca of São Paulo State, Brazil. The sticky cards were replaced fortnightly from November 2017 to December 2018. Among > 10 species of sharpshooter and spittlebug trapped, *Acrogonia citrina* and *Oncometopia facialis* were the most frequent at 7.5 m, with total catches of 1,681 and 123 individuals, respectively. The proportions of individuals trapped at 7.5 m were higher for *A. citrina* (18–48%) than *O. facialis* (12–21%), with the highest values recorded in Botucatu. Insects were trapped at 7.5 m throughout the year, but more frequently in summer and/or fall. The results suggest that sharpshooters are strong fliers and may engage in wind-assisted flights, possibly carrying *X. fastidiosa* over long distances.

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Determination of potential vectors of *Xylella fastidiosa* in Costa Rican coffee plantations

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Abstract: *Xylella fastidiosa* is a vector-transmitted plant pathogen of economic importance. In Costa Rica, *X. fastidiosa*-positive coffee plants are mostly asymptomatic, or present mild symptoms related to 'crespera' disease, as reported previously. Broad genetic diversity of circulating *X. fastidiosa* strains isolated from coffee is another trait present in this country. Despite this, there is scarce information regarding vector biology in this pathosystem. Past studies have shown that there is great diversity of Hemiptera (Cicadellidae and Cercopidae) in coffee production zones affected by *X. fastidiosa* in Costa Rica; these insects represent potential *X. fastidiosa* vectors. However, to our knowledge, confirmation of vector status remains unsettled. In this work, we identified within the population of Cicadellidae and Cercopidae from a coffee plantation in Carrizal, Alajuela province, a coffee-producing zone in the northern region of the Central Valley, three specific species of leafhoppers as true vectors of *X. fastidiosa* related to coffee in Costa Rica. To achieve these results, insects were collected from infected coffee fields, and Cicadellidae were identified, classified and grouped for further analysis. All assays were set up in greenhouse conditions. The ability of these vectors to feed on healthy coffee plants was assessed. Artificial transmission assays revealed the presence of the bacteria, using qPCR after a 24 h feeding period. MLST typing was performed on positive feeding solutions to confirm circulating ST. Transmission assays were performed on healthy coffee plants that were free of *X. fastidiosa*, detection of the bacteria was achieved in plants as early as three months, positive plants have not shown symptoms for up to six months. These findings contribute to the integral understanding of the pathosystem and for the development of mitigation strategies.

Surveys for vectors and candidate vectors of *Xylella fastidiosa* in olive orchards in Apulia

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Abstract: For three consecutive years, surveys were conducted in 24 olive orchards located in the demarcated *Xylella*-infected area of Apulia (southern Italy), with the aim of identifying xylem-feeder species serving as vector of *Xylella fastidiosa* in olives. Surveys were carried out periodically from spring to late autumn and insects were collected by sweeping net using constant sampling units from olive canopies, ground vegetation and border plants when present. All insects were subjected to qPCR for the detection of *X. fastidiosa* (individually or in groups of 5), as well as to the morphological identification. Besides the two spittlebug vectors (*Philaenus spumarius* and *Neophilaenus campestris*), more than 3,000 specimens belonging to 37 different species (27 Cicadomorpha and 10 Fulgoromorpha) of 34 genera and 10 families were collected. The detection of the bacterium in spittlebugs, xylem-feeders and on some of the most abundant phloem-limited species, showed that: (i) for the two known vectors occurring in the area, a higher incidence of positive specimens was detected for *P. spumarius* (up to 50%) with the occurrence of *Xylella*-positive insects for a prolonged period, compared with *N. campestris* (10% of positive specimens, detected to a limited extent in late spring), and (ii) for both species the incidence of positive specimens was consistently higher when they were collected from olive canopies compared with ground vegetation or border plants; (iii) amongst the xylem-feeders, none of the specimens collected and tested for *Cicada orni*, *Cercopis sanguinolenta* and *Lepyronia coleoptrata* were found positive; (iv) conversely, few positive specimens were recovered for the following leafhoppers and planthoppers: *Thamnotettix zelleri* (8.33% in olives and 3.7% in weeds); *Latilica tunetana* (1.77% in olives, 2.2% in weeds) and for *Euscellis lineolatus* (none in olives, 0.06% in weeds). Regarding the possible role as vector of *X. fastidiosa* for these planthopper/leafhopper species, transmission tests have already excluded the capability of the *L. tunetana* to retain and transmit the bacterium, whereas experimental tests are ongoing for *T. zelleri*.

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Tacking *Phylaenus spumarius* through geo-statistical analysis of field observations and identification of wild fennel as a key host herbaceous species during the insect early growth development

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Abstract: *Philaenus spumarius* L., the meadow froghopper, is actually assessed as the main carrier of *Xylella fastidiosa* in the Mediterranean basin. In a previous study, aimed to improve the understanding of the insect's nutritional behaviour, especially at its critical nymph stage, by monitoring its presence on different herbaceous target species, we used typical feeding foams as key indicators (Latini et al. 2019). The study area was in the Lazio region (central Italy), dedicated to olive growing and still unaffected by the *Xylella* plague. In the last five years, during the nymph development period, field data have been acquired over the test areas and then analysed by coupling statistics, geographical information system (GIS) and georeferenced field sampling. Results highlight that *P. spumarius* exhibits some preferences for specific herbaceous plants, especially at its early development stages, detectable by a very tenuous spittle; thus it is possible to speculate that a defined mechanism leading to the plant choice exists, driving the females at the time of oviposition.

Applied implications arising from these findings for *P. spumarius* population management are discussed. Indeed, our attention has shifted the focus from the three well-known targets, i.e. the olive tree plantation, *X. fastidiosa* and *P. spumarius*, to a restricted identified group of herbaceous plants that look particularly attractive for the insect carrier at its early growth stage. As confirmed during further several field observations, under the